
ITEM PSYCHOMETRIC PROPERTIES AND STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: AN ANALYSIS OF 2022 MATHEMATICS PLACEMENT EXAMINATIONS IN HADEJIA TOWN, JIGAWA STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed at investigating item difficulty level and discrimination power of 2022 Mathematics Placement Examinations in Hadejia Town, Jigawa State, with a view to find out mean differences in facility index and Discrimination power ability of the items in the Examination between male and female students. The population of the study consist of all students who sat for Mathematics Placement Examinations in Hadejia Town in the year 2022. A sample of 382 students was drawn from the population, and multi-stage cluster sampling technique was used in drawing the sample. The instrument of the study is the student's marked scripts. Data analysis was carried out by the researcher using SPSS to obtain item difficulty indices and discrimination power indices. Findings from the study revealed that 23.33% of the items were of poor difficulty level and 46.67% were poor in terms of discrimination power ability. In the same vein, the results indicated no significant difference in mean difficulty level and discrimination power ability between Male and Female students in Hadejia Town, Jigawa State. It's recommended that item analysis should be encouraged in test development stage of Placement Examinations, and test expert should be employed mainly for construction and analysis of the items.

Keywords: *Item analysis, item difficulty index, item discrimination index, placement Examinations*

INTRODCUTION

Acceptability and accuracy of test results depends on the procedures followed while developing, administering and scoring the test items. Proper adherence to principles involved in the procedure drives accuracy, transparency and minimize grade bias, contributing to rigor and dependability. Making fair and systematic evaluations of other's performance can be a challenging task. Judgments cannot be made solely on the basis of intuition, haphazard guessing, or custom. People in evaluative positions use a variety of tools to assist them in their evaluations.

Tests are tools that are frequently used to facilitate the evaluation process. Developing perfect test is the unattainable goal for anyone in an evaluative position. Even when guidelines for constructing fair and systematic tests are followed, some factors may hinder development of a good test. Looking at an item's difficulty and discrimination will assist the test developer in determining what is wrong with individual items. Item and test analysis provide empirical data about how individual items and whole tests are performing in real test situations (Karkal and Kundapur, 2016).

Item difficulty is simply the percentage of students taking the test who answered the item correctly. The larger the percentage getting an item right, the easier the item. The higher difficulty index, the easier item is understood to be. Item difficulty has a profound effect on both variability of test scores and the precision with which test scores discriminate among different groups of examinees. Item discrimination on the other hand detects the ability of a test item to discriminate between high achievers and low achievers. When a test item can not differentiate between low and high achievers, such an item would not be considered as a good item. Meaning it lacks some qualities to be included in an instrument geared towards grading and awarding certificates to the test takers. Distracter effectiveness connotes ability of the distracters to attract attention of the test takers from the key. A good distracter is one which hijacks the attention of the test takers to contemplate on the key in an objective question. A distracter which cannot perform such function is termed "non-functional distracters.

Statement of the Problem

Teacher- made tests of which Jigawa State Placement Examinations is one, lack proper content validation. Faulty evaluation process may lead to wrong placement of students. One of the processes of good evaluation is the development of good evaluation instrument that will serve the purpose for which it is intended. Unless a test instrument is validated it will not provide accurate information about students' learning outcome. Placement Examinations is one of the major Examinations administered by State Universal Basic Education Board (SUBEB) in Jigawa state. It is designed to mainly test and place students to various courses in Senior Secondary Schools. Mathematics is one of the foundation subjects taught at both primary and senior secondary levels and is one of the core subjects at both primary, junior and senior secondary levels of education. For a student to fulfil the requirements for placement into science classes at senior secondary schools. Admission into any institution of higher learning in Nigeria requires a student to pass Mathematics at credit level in their senior secondary school examinations.

Evaluation is one of the vital methods used in transition, grading and certification in our educational system. Being systematic, evaluation needs to be carried out with expertise especially when placing students in an appropriate area of studies. As an indispensable aspect of test development and validation item analysis of all tests has become necessary. As quality

of test becomes central to all decisions taken on a particular test, validity of 2022 Multiple Choice Question (MCQ) of Mathematics Placement Examinations in Hadejia Town, Jigawa State needs to be investigated. And this could be done through item analysis to establish the quality of the items therein.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study are to find out;

1. The item facility index of 2022 Mathematics placement Examinations in Hadejia, Town Jigawa state.
2. The item discrimination power ability of 2022 Mathematics placement Examinations in Hadejia Town, Jigawa state.
3. The mean difference in the item's facility index of 2022 Mathematics Placement Examinations between male and Female Students in Hadejia, Town Jigawa State.
4. Mean difference in the item's discrimination power ability of 2022 Mathematics Placement Examinations between Male and Female Students in Hadejia, Town Jigawa State.

Research Questions

In order to archive objectives one (1) and two (2) the following questions were raised;

1. What are the item facility index of 2022 Mathematics placement Examinations in Hadejia, Town Jigawa state?
2. What are the item discrimination power ability of 2022 Mathematics placement Examinations in Hadejia Town, Jigawa state?

Research Hypothesis

In order to archive objectives 3 and 4, the following hypotheses were formulated;

H01: There is no significant mean difference in facility index of 2022 Mathematics Placement Examinations between male and Female Students in Hadejia town Jigawa State.

H02: There is no significant mean difference in discrimination power of 2022 Mathematics Placement Examinations between Male and Female Students in Hadejia town, Jigawa State.

Materials and Methods

Ex-post facto research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study consist of all students who sat for 2022 Mathematics Examinations in Hadejia Town, Jigawa State numbering 12800 students. A sample of 382 students was drawn from the population in line with the justification of sample size by Research advisors Table (Research Advisors, 2006), and multi-stage sampling technique was been used in drawing sample. Starting by cluster sampling and completing by simple random sampling by the use of hat and draw. The instrument of the study is the student's marked scripts). Pro-forma was designed where students' scores were entered. Data analysis was carried out by the researcher using SPSS in obtaining item difficulty, discrimination power. t-test independent sample were used to find out whether there is significant difference in mean difficulty level and discrimination power of 2022 Mathematics Placement Examinations. Data for both genders were considered as equal i.e There was no discrimination in the data between male and female students. Since the research involves analyzing Examinations results of students, results and identity of the

students has been kept with outmost care. Privacy and confidentiality of the data has been highly considered.

RESULTS

The study aimed at investigating item facility index and discrimination power of 2022 mathematics placement Examinations in Hadejia town, Jigawa State, with a view to find mean differences in item difficulty and item discrimination between male and female students.

Research Question 1. *What are the items facility index of 2022 Mathematics placement Examinations in Hadejia town Jigawa state?*

Item facility of each item in 2022 Mathematics Placement Examinations were determined by following the CTT principle of selecting the top and bottom 27% of the tests for obtaining this item characteristics, the number of students in upper and lower group who got the item right was obtained by frequency count and the proportion of students getting the item was calculated. The difficulty indices were then obtained and summarized in table 1. The researcher used quality criterion recommended by Anikweze (2012), Alonge (2003), and Anastasi (2014).

Table 1: Showing Item difficulty level of 2022 Mathematics Placement Examinations in Jigawa State with Range of difficulty, percentages and Descriptions.

Ranges of Difficulty	Item Number	Number of items	Percentages	Description
0-14%		0	0	Very difficult
15-29%	17,20,29,30	4	13.33%	Difficult
30-69%	3,4,7,10,13,14,15,18,21,25	10	33.33%	Moderately difficult
70-84%	2,5,6,8,9,16,24,26,28	9	30%	Easy
85-100%	1,11,12,19,22,23,27	7	23.33%	Very Easy
TOTAL	30	30	100	

From Table 1, one could see that 4 items (13.33%) of the items were difficult, 10 items (33.33%) of the items were moderately difficult, 9 items representing 30% of the items are easy and 7 items representing 23.33% of the items are very easy. No item falls within the description of very difficult. It is therefore concluded that, only 23.33% of the items are poor in terms of difficulty.

Research Question 2. *What are the item discrimination power ability of 2022 Mathematics Placement Examinations in Hadejia town, Jigawa state?*

To answer this question simple percentage was employed. The researcher used the quality criterion recommended by Alonge (2003), Anikweze (2012) and Anastasi & Urbina (2014).

Table 2: Showing Item discrimination power of 2022 Mathematics Examinations in Hadejia town Jigawa state with Ranges of discrimination, percentages and descriptions

Ranges of discrimination indices	Items number	Total number of items	Percentages	Description
Negative Items	0	0	0	Very poor
0.00-0.18	1,2,4,7,10,11,12,13,15,16,19,26,27,29	14	46.67%	Poor
0.19-0.29	3,5,6,8,9,17,18,20,23,	9	30%	Moderate
0.30-0.39	14,21,24,25,	4	13.33%	Good
0.40-1.00	22,28,30	3	10%	Very good
TOTAL	30	30	100%	

From Table 2, above, one could see that, 14 items, representing 46.67% of the items has poor discriminating power ability, 9 items representing only 30% has moderate discriminating index, 4 items, representing 13.33% has good discrimination power ability and 3 items, representing 10% of the items were very good respectively.

Ho1: There is no significant mean difference in facility index of 2022 Mathematics Placement Examinations between male and Female Students in Hadejia town Jigawa State.

Table 3: t-test table of the mean facility index of 2022 Placement Examinations in Hadejia town, Jigawa State

Subjects	N	Mean	t	p	sig.
Male	30	0.14	1.57	.12	.05
Female	30	0.09			

Source: SPSS

The above table 3 showed the value of t equals to 1.57, p-value 0.122. Since the value of $P > .05$ the null hypothesis is true. This leads to conclusion that there is no significant difference in mean facility index of 2022 Mathematics Examinations between Male and Female in Hadejia town, Jigawa State.

Ho2: There is no significant mean difference in discrimination power of 2022 Mathematics Placement Examinations between Male and Female Students in Hadejia town, Jigawa State.

Table 4: t-test table of the mean discrimination power of 2022 Placement Examinations in Hadejia Town Jigawa State

Subjects	N	Mean	t	p	sig.
Male	30	.32	-.74	.46	.05
Female	30	.37			

Source: SPSS

From table 4 above, it could be seen that, t is $-.74$ and p value is $.46$ at $.05$ level of significance. Since $P > .05$, the null hypothesis is true, and it's concluded that, there is no significant difference in mean discrimination power of 2022 Mathematics Examinations between Male and Female students in Hadejia town, Jigawa state.

DISCUSSIONS

The objectives of the study were to investigate the quality of items in 2022 Mathematics Placement Examinations developed by JERD in Jigawa state, by finding out their difficulty level and discrimination power ability as well as investigating whether mean significant difference exists in mean difficulty indices and discrimination power ability between Male and Female Students in Hadejia town, Jigawa State. From Research Question one (1), one could observe that, only 23.33% of the items were poor and 76.67% were good in terms of difficulty. This study is not in agreement that of Iliyasu (2023) and Sani (2014) who concluded that, only 25% and 30% of 2017 Senior Secondary School Qualifying Examinations in Jigawa State and 2013 English Language Placement Examinations in Jigawa State are good. Nevertheless, this finding is in agreement with that of Abubakar (2015) whose finding revealed that, majority of the items (71%) was good as far as difficulty is concern. On the basis of discrimination power ability, the result from the study indicated that, 46.67% items are poor, meaning 53.33% of the items was good. The finding is in line with that of Sani (2014) who found out that 55% of the 2012 English Placement Examinations in Jigawa State had good discrimination power. The study is not in agreement with that of Danjuma (2018) and Iliyasu (2023) who reported 62.6% and 60% of 2017 English Language Common Entrance Examinations in Jigawa state and 2017 Mathematics Senior Secondary School Qualifying Examinations in Jigawa state were poor respectively. the result from the study, call for the retention of the two null hypotheses and concluded that, there is no significant difference in mean difficulty level and discrimination power ability of the test items between Male and Female Students in Hadejia Town, Jigawa State, and this is consistent with findings of Danjuma (2018) and Iliyasu (2023) who revealed no significant difference in mean difficulty level and discrimination power ability of the 2017 English Language common Entrance Examinations between conventional and nomadic primary schools pupils in Jigawa State and 2017 Mathematics Senior Secondary School Qualifying Examinations between Male and Female Students in Jigawa State. This study is not in agreement with that of Mustapha S.H and Abdullahi I. (2023) who revealed a significant difference in Mean difficulty level and Discrimination power ability of 2014 Mathematics Qualifying Examinations in Hadejia Zone, Jigawa State.

Conclusion

From the analysis above, it is concluded that, most of the items in the instrument are good in terms of difficulty and discrimination index, even though the percentage of the poor items are relatively high and need refinement. And the study shows no evidence of significant difference in mean difficulty and discrimination indices between Male and Female students in Hadejia town, Jigawa State.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, following recommendations were been made;

1. JERD should pilot-test Placement Examinations before administering it to the students.
2. Test expert should be employed by JERD who will be charged with responsibilities of construction, administration and scoring procedure for the items.

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